

Local Government in Ethiopia

Responses to Urban-Rural Challenges

edited by

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The H2020-MSCA-RISE-2018 project aims to provide solutions for local governments that address the fundamental challenges resulting from urbanisation. To address these complex issues, 18 partners from 17 countries and six continents share their expertise and knowledge in the realms of public law, political science, and public administration. LoGov identifies, evaluates, compares, and shares innovative practices that cope with the impact of changing urban-rural relations in major local government areas (WP 1-5).

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Local Responsibilities and Public Services

2.1. Local Responsibilities and Public Services in Ethiopia: An Introduction

Zemelak Ayele, *Centre for Federalism and Governance Studies, Addis Ababa University*

Studies show that it is imperative that the functional competences of local government in the areas of service delivery are suitable and clearly defined in a constitution or statutory documents. The responsibilities should be suitable in a sense that they should be within the financial and human capacity of local government lest it should be overburdened with complex responsibilities that are beyond its capacity.²¹ Subsidiarity is seen as the best approach in terms of determining the suitability of a certain functional area to local government.

It is important to define local government's responsibilities preferably in a national constitution or other legislative document.²² This helps counter any temptation from the central government to centralize local government responsibilities. Moreover, studies suggest that the definition of the competences of local government should be clear but not too detailed lest senior levels of government should prescribe what local government should do in the name of defining their competences thereby compromising their autonomy.²³ Clearly defining local government's responsibilities has several benefits:

- it becomes clear what services local authorities are expected to provide;
- it prevents duplication of efforts;
- it allows local citizens where to go when seeking certain public services;
- it also makes holding local authorities accountable, electorally or otherwise, when they fail to deliver on their mandates.

The 1995 Constitution of Ethiopia is silent on the functional competences of local government. Having established a dual federal system, it only lists the competences of the federal and state governments. It indeed enjoins the states to devolve 'adequate' responsibilities to local government without actually defining their responsibilities.²⁴ So, one would expect the states to define the responsibilities of local government in state constitutions. However, the state constitutions provide in general terms that local government has the power to decide on local social, developmental and economic matters without defining what those are. The question is what functional competences the states transferred to local government. Practice and other subnational legislative documents provide some indication regarding the responsibilities of local government.

²¹ James Manor, *The Political Economy of Democratic Decentralization* (World Bank 1999).

²² Jaap de Visser, *Developmental Local Government: A Case Study of South Africa* (Intersentia 2005).

²³ Francis N Botchway, 'Good Governance: The Old, the New, the Principle, and the Elements' (2001) 13 Florida Journal of International Law 160.

²⁴ Art 50(4), FDRE Constitution (1995).

As indicated in report section 1, there are two categories of local government in Ethiopia: the ethnic local government and regular local government. The first is established based on the federal principle that provides ethnic communities the right to self-determination. The local government units in this category are nationality zones and *liyu woredas*. These units are in general responsible for promoting and protecting the cultural identity of the relevant ethnic communities. Their responsibilities thus relate to the promotion of the language and culture of the relevant ethnic communities.²⁵The regular local governments are in turn divided into rural *woredas* and urban local government (cities). The *woredas*, which are rural local government units, exercise certain competences in different functional areas. The functional areas that *woredas* exercise are informed by the policy of poverty reduction which underpinned the whole decentralization program which was launched in the early 2000s. Thus, the functional areas of *woredas* include the following:

- primary and secondary education (grades 1-10)
 - adult education
 - printing and distributing primary school textbooks
 - administering primary school
- health extension services
 - constructing and administering health stations and health posts
 - administering clinics
 - controlling and preventing HIV/AIDS and malaria
- constructing wells
 - supplying drinking water to municipalities
- planning and implementing agricultural and pastoral development
 - implementing agriculture extension packages
 - constructing and administering small-scale indigenous irrigation
- constructing rural roads connecting *kebeles*
- implementing state functions in municipalities within a *woreda*

The cities have two types of responsibilities: state functions and municipal functions. The state functions are those services that *woredas* provide and are linked with poverty reduction. These include primary education, primary health care, and the like. Their municipal functions relate to typical urban services such as garbage collection, sewerage, registration of birth and death.

²⁵ Zemelak Ayele, *Local Government in Ethiopia: Advancing Development and Accommodating Ethnic Minorities* (Nomos 2014).

References to Scientific and Non-Scientific Publications

Legal Documents:

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